

‘THRIFTING’ AS FASHION TREND AMONG GEN-Z: FACTORS INFLUENCING PURCHASE INTENTION ON SECOND-HAND CLOTHING IN INDONESIA

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Abstract:

Thrifting is a term used in consumer behavior in searching and purchasing secondary products, but in this study, the focus is on buying used clothes. This study aims to examine the relationship between people's buying interest in thrifting influenced by perceptions of second-hand clothing, consumer lifestyle, social media influencers, and brands. The method used in this research is to use a survey conducted on 390 people from generation Z in Indonesia who have done thrifting. All results were analyzed and verified using SEM-PLS. This study found that perceptions of second-hand clothing, consumer lifestyle, and brands positively affect people's buying interest in thrifting. The data also shows that brands have the most substantial relationship with purchase intention in 'thrifting', while social media influencers are the lowest aspect.

Keywords: Perception of Second-Hand Clothing, Consumer Lifestyle, Social Media Influencers, Brands, Purchase Intentions, Thrifting, Fashion, Indonesia.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Communication technology is growing, contributing too many changes in all aspects of life. These changes can also indirectly affect lifestyles, societal trends, and others. In addition, fashion is also an industry that is significantly affected by technological changes (Park and Kim, 2001). It can be said that nowadays, fashion is essential for some people in their daily life. Developments and fashion changes can occur because with technology can see various fashions other people wear. In addition, fashion changes also impact people's behavior in buying used clothes, or what is currently known as 'thrifting'.

The definition of thrifting itself is a term used in the activity of buying used goods. However, what is currently popular is thrifting on clothes. Thus, this research will focus on thrifting clothes (fashion). Currently, thrifting is becoming a popular culture in the community. This statement is reinforced by Kwan (2017), who states that buying and selling used clothes or fashion is becoming popular. According to data released by Medium (2019), it is stated that the interest in thrifting is dominated by Generation Z, reaching 46%.

Not only developing in western countries, but now thrifting is also starting to be loved by the younger generation in Indonesia, especially generation Z. The popularity of thrifting can be

seen from the data recorded by BPS (Central Statistics Agency), which recorded that in January - October 2021, imported clothing amounted to 58.1 tons, totaling US\$517.2 million or Rp7.34 trillion (Solopos.com, 2021). Indirectly, this can illustrate that the public's interest and interest in thrifting or purchasing second-hand clothing (SHC) is high. Several internal and external factors undoubtedly influence the high public interest in thrifting. Previous research (Amaral and Spers, 2022) stated that a person's perception of second-hand clothing would influence a person's intention to consume second-hand clothing and change the behavior of consumers. The definition of perception itself is how humans think about an idea or thing (Qiong, 2017). Where what is a person's view or assessment of second-hand clothing is essential in buying intentions. Moreover, according to Kotler and Keller (2016), everyone perceives an object differently, even with the same object. Thus, it is necessary to conduct further research to determine whether a person's perception of second-hand clothing can influence their purchase intention or vice versa.

Then, there is a study that has been done by Hawkins et al. (2010) which states that a person's lifestyle can affect all aspects of a person's consumption. Thus, it can be assumed that a person's lifestyle also influences how and what they consume. Supporting this statement, Sakti et al. (2020) stated that a person's purchase intention is significantly influenced by lifestyle. A person's lifestyle is dynamic or changes over time because some lifestyles are shaped by time and money constraints (Kotler and Keller, 2012). Thus, the change in a person's lifestyle from time to time seems to be the statement above, and it needs to be explored further to find out whether a person's lifestyle has anything to do with that person's purchase intention.

As previously mentioned, a person's purchase intention is influenced by several factors. One of them is marketing, which is currently being done using social media. However, according to data released by eMarketer (2017), it states that compared to content created directly by the company, currently, content created by social media influencers has a more significant impact on consumer purchasing decisions. There are still not many studies that specifically discuss the influence of social media influencers on someone's buying interest in second-hand clothing (thrifting). By seeing this, this study is interested in finding out whether social media influencers also influence someone's purchase intention on second-hand clothing (thrifting) or vice versa. Not only in marketing, but what is contained in an object or product is also considered essential. One of them is a brand, which can show ownership of a company, which can be felt, experienced, evaluated, and builds an association to understand a value (Elliot et al., 2015). Thus, this study is interested in seeing whether a brand in second-hand will be able to influence someone's purchase intention in buying second-hand clothing (thrifting).

Based on previous research, only a few studies use data to analyze buying interest in SHC (thrifting), especially in Indonesia. This research is expected to be able to take that position, as one of the novelties in the field of fashion. To get better insight from different perspectives, this study aims to examine whether there is a relationship between perception of second-hand clothing (SHC), consumer lifestyle, social media influencers, and brands with purchase intention on second-hand clothing (thrifting). Especially by Generation Z in Indonesia.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical Background

This research adopts the theoretical basis of the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA). Martin Fishbein and Icek Ajzen developed this theory to identify a component that predicts behavior. The purpose of developing this theory is to explain the influence on behavior, which involves conscious decision-making (Greene, 2009). This theory was developed to understand the relationship between attitudes, behavior, and intentions. According to Ajzen (1991), the greater intention to engage in a behavior, the more likely the behavior is carried out. So, if someone has a positive attitude toward a behavior, they will tend to form positive intentions toward it (Manaktola and Jauhari, 2007). Thus, this study uses TRA as a basis to explore what factors can influence a person's purchase intention on second-hand clothing (thrifting) with the independent variable perception of second-hand clothing (SHC), consumer lifestyle, social media influencers, and brands.

2.2 Perception of Second-hand Clothing (SHC)

Perception is the human way of thinking about a thing or idea (Qiong, 2017). Perception is also a process in which individuals organize, select, and interpret information, creating a meaningful picture of the world. This type of information can later be felt by their senses (Kotler and Keller, 2016). Then, the definition of second-hand clothing (SHC) is a piece of clothing that previously belonged to someone else. So, it can be said that the perception of SHC is how a person assesses or views SHC from several sides or points of view. A person's perception of something can influence a person's level of consumption of a thing. There are three dimensions of perception of second-hand clothing: socio-environmental awareness, preconception with second-hand clothes, and need for personal uniqueness.

2.3 Consumer Lifestyle

In simple terms, lifestyle can be defined as a way of life or a person's desire to live. Lifestyle refers to the way of life of consumers, which is expressed through activities, interests, and opinions (Kotler and Armstrong, 2018). Solomon (2020) states that lifestyle analysis of consumers can provide greater insight into how one can spend money and time. According to Hawkins et al. (2010), lifestyle is considered to be able to influence all aspects of a person's consumption behavior. Based on the explanation above, it can be said that consumer lifestyle is how a consumer lives.

Kotler and Keller (2012) states that part of a lifestyle is shaped by time and money constraints. This statement is supported by Kim and Kim (2020), who state that socio-demographic characteristics, such as gender, age, education, marital status, health, and economic status, have an essential role in lifestyle and motivation. According to Aguilar-Rodríguez and Arias-Bolzmann (2021), one of the most common ways to understand lifestyle is to use the AIO (Activity, Interest, and Opinion) model. The AIO approach was first introduced by Wells and Tigert (1971) to analyze consumer lifestyles. Thus, this study will use the AIO model as a lifestyle dimension.

2.4 Brand

According to the American Marketing Association (AMA), a brand is a name, sign, symbol, term, design, or a combination of them with the intent to identify the goods or services of one or a group of sellers of goods or services (Kotler and Keller, 2016). Brands can also show ownership of a company that we can feel, experience, evaluate, and build associations to understand a value (Elliot et al., 2015). Kotler and Keller (2016) states that a brand can affect consumers' pride, confidence, and enthusiasm. Besides that, thrifting is also a place for those who want to get branded goods at lower prices (Tinkcom et al., 2002). In addition, brand awareness and image can positively influence brand equity, which is known to contribute to customer loyalty, purchase decisions, brand preferences, and consumer responses (Godey et al., 2016). It can be said that the development of positive consumer attitudes can be fulfilled by fostering consumer excellence and trust, which is obtained from a brand's associations (Putri and Rohimakumullah, 2022).

2.5 Social Media Influencers

Nowadays, influencer marketing is often applied as one of the marketing strategies run by a company. This marketing strategy emphasizes using influencers as a medium to convey messages to reach the target (Lim et al., 2017). According to Najmi et al. (2019), marketing activities are crucial to encourage consumers to buy a product. Currently, a business has integrated social media as a communication strategy to influence customers' purchasing decisions (Lariscy et al., 2009; Dankwa, 2021). Thus, it is not surprising that social media influencers have been considered third-party supporters who help in marketing the business and determining attitudes (Freberg et al., 2011) because it was found that content created by influencers had a more significant impact on consumer purchases, compared to content created directly by Instagram (eMarketer, 2017). Product promotions carried out by social media influencers are by writing reviews or exciting information about a product to attract customers (Sharma and Ranga, 2014). Then, the media that is often used by social media influencers for promotion is through social media platforms, such as Instagram, YouTube, Facebook, TikTok, and Twitter (Lim et al., 2017). For influencers, attractiveness, trustworthiness, and expertise must be considered to see someone's purchase intention (AlFarraj, 2021).

2.6 Purchase Intention

Purchase intention is the possibility that a consumer will buy a product or service in the future (Arslan and Zaman, 2014). Purchase intention can also be said to be a type of decision-making that studies why consumers buy a particular product or brand (Shah et al., 2012). In line with Lu et al. (2014), purchase intention can also be interpreted as a consumer's plan to buy a product that involves certain circumstances and times when consumers want to buy a product. A positive purchase intention can encourage consumers to make actual purchases. Meanwhile, negative purchase intentions can discourage consumers from buying something (Mahmoud, 2018). It can happen because a purchase intention indicates how much a person wants to approach a particular behavior and how much effort they make to try to approach that behavior

(Ajzen, 1991). In addition, according to Ling (2010), there are four indicators of purchase intention: transactional, referential, preferential, and explorative.

2.7 Thrifting

Thrifting is a term used to look for or buy used goods. Gulfira (2018) defines thrifting as an activity of finding used goods in certain places. Furthermore, these used goods can be obtained from thrift stores, garage sales, or flea markets (Ronobir, 2020). There are various types of goods in thrifting, such as clothes, shoes, electronic goods, and others. However, the clothing category is now becoming popular in the community. The types of clothing generally sold at thrift stores are sweaters, jackets, t-shirts, shirts, hoodies, pants, and many more. Not infrequently, the clothes sold are products from various well-known brands. In general, the SHC sold by thrift stores are imported clothes whose condition is still suitable for use (Lestari and Asmarani, 2021).

2.8 Gen-Z (Generation Z)

Generation Z is a term for those born in the vulnerable years 1995 – 2012, which is also commonly known as “Me Generation”, Generation N”, and “Digital Natives” (Feiertag and Berge, 2008). According to Turner (2015), Generation Z is the first generation to be directly exposed to a technology widely. In this way, the development of characteristics in generation Z is also influenced by the environment, which coincides with the development of increasingly sophisticated media and technology (Dwidienawati and Gandasari, 2018).

3.0 RESEARCH FRAMEWORK

Figure 1 is a framework for this research, which can provide a brief description of the relationship between the independent variables and their effect on the dependent variable.

Figure 1: The research framework

Source: Developed by the author

3.1 Study Hypotheses

Based on the above research framework and the influence of independent variables on the dependent variable, the following hypotheses can be drawn:

H₁: Perception of SHC has a positive relationship with SHC purchase intention

H₀: Perception of SHC has a negative relationship with SHC purchase intention

H₂: Consumer lifestyle has a positive relationship with SHC purchase intention

H₀: Consumer lifestyle has a negative relationship with SHC purchase intention

H₃: Social media influencer has a positive relationship with SHC purchase intention

H₀: Social media influencer has a negative relationship with SHC purchase intention

H₄: Brand has a positive relationship with SHC purchase intention

H₀: Brand has a negative relationship with SHC purchase intention

4.0 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study adopts the positivism paradigm because it is possible to measure information that can be measured. This study uses a quantitative approach, with the type of explanatory research, which explains the relationship between one variable and another to test the hypothesis. According to Adler and Clark (2014), exploratory research tends to move from something general to something less familiar. Using a quantitative research design, this research uses a survey as the primary data collection method that is a questionnaire. The survey method collects information from a sample of individuals through their responses to a question (Check and Schutt, 2012). The purpose of using this method is that in this study, we want to find out how someone responds to anything that can encourage their intention to buy thrifting products, by using questionnaire. The use of survey methods in research also aims to find, collect, and analyze data in a sample group, such as attitudes, opinions, and beliefs (Stack, 2010). It is in line with the statement of Singleton and Stairts (2009), which states that surveys are often used in social research.

The population the survey in this study was conducted on men or women in generation Z in Indonesia, especially in the cities of Jakarta, Bogor, Depok, Tangerang, and Bekasi (Jabodetabek). Due to the inability to collect complete and concrete data on the study population, non-probability sampling will be used in this study as a sampling technique. In addition, this study uses purposive sampling, where the researcher will determine the sample criteria following the research objectives. The criteria for the sample in this study were male and female; 17-27 years old (in 2022); actively use social media; have purchased second-hand clothing (thrifting) in the past year; domiciled in the cities of Jakarta, Bogor, Depok, Tangerang and Bekasi in Indonesia. In collecting research data, the questionnaire has been rigorously tested and developed. The questionnaire was made through Google Forms using a Likert scale to measure the extent to which respondents agreed through the question items in the questionnaire.

Determination of the number of samples to be taken in this study using the formula from Lemeshow. Because the Lemeshow formula can be used in research where the population's exact number is unknown (Menard, 2010), with the formula $Z^2(1-\alpha)/2P(1-P)/d^2$, which consists of the z score at the 95% confidence level (1.96); the proportion of the unknown population 50% (0.5); and the value of alpha (d) at an error rate of 5% (0.05) found a sample value of 384 respondents. Of the 450 questionnaires that have been distributed, 390 questionnaires were obtained, which are considered valid for hypothesis testing. The Smart-PLS version 3.2.9 application will be used for data processing from the questionnaire results that have been obtained.

5.0 FINDING AND ANALYSIS OF RESULT

5.1 Descriptive Statistics

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of Respondents

Profile of Respondents	Statement	Freq.	%
Gender	Male	104	26.7
	Female	286	73.3
Age	17–19	125	32.1
	20–22	195	50
	23–27	70	17.9
Domicile	Jakarta	163	41.8
	Bogor	48	12.3
	Depok	30	7.7
	Tangerang	89	22.8
	Bekasi	60	15.4
Type of Work	Student / College Student	290	74.4
	Private Employees	71	18.2
	Civil Servants	3	0.76
	Entrepreneur	13	3.3
	Housewife	5	1.28
	Etc	8	2.05
Outcome Level	< Rp1,000,000	248	63.6
	Rp1,000,000 – Rp6,000,000	134	34.4
	> Rp6,000,000	8	2.1
Social Media Platform Mostly Used	Instagram	352	30.6
	TikTok	230	20
	Facebook	37	3.2
	Twitter	84	7.3
	Youtube	85	7.4
	WhatsApp	272	23.8
	Line	84	7.3
	Etc	8	0.7

Source: Based on this research

Table 1 presents statistics from research data from 390 respondents consisting of 104 (26.7%) males and 286 (73.3%) females. Respondents aged 20-22 fulfilled 50% of the total sample, namely 195 people. Meanwhile, respondents aged 23-27 were the minority respondents, with as many as 70 respondents (17.9%). Then 41.8% of respondents live in Jakarta City, around 163 people, and Depok City is the minority domicile of the respondents, around 30 people (7.7%). Furthermore, the respondents in this study were also dominated by students or college students, as many as 290 people (74.4%). This figure is more than 50% of the sample of respondents but compared to the number of respondents whose work status is as a housewife, that is five people (1.28%). The other types of work chosen are respondents who work as freelancers, baristas, production operators, content creators, and those who have not worked. Regarding expenditure level, 63.6% of respondents have expenditures of less than Rp. 1,000,000, while the other eight respondents (2.1%) have expenses of more than Rp. 6,000,000.

Of course, at the beginning of the questionnaire, they were asked whether they had previously done 'thrift' or bought second-hand clothing in one last year. If so, they can move on to the next section and vice versa. Then respondents were also asked whether they were active in using social media. The study results showed that 390 people indicated that they had bought second-hand clothing (thrift) in the past year and actively used social media. In addition, respondents were also asked to choose 1-3 social media they use the most. From the data obtained, 352 respondents (30.6) actively use Instagram.

5.2 Evaluation of Measurement Model

5.2.1 Convergent Validity Analysis

This test was conducted on the question items contained in the questionnaire. In the convergent validity test, what needs to be considered are the loading factor and average variance extracted (AVE), where convergent validity can be met if the AVE value is more than 0.5. In contrast, the latent variable indicator can be considered sufficient and significant if the loading value in each dimension reaches 0.6. Table 2 shows that the overall AVE value and loading value in each dimension are met from the previously mentioned value limits.

Table 2: Reliability and Confirmatory Factor Analysis

Construct	Item	Loading Item	AVE
Perception of Second-hand Clothing	PSHC1	0.670	0.514
	PSHC2	0.706	
	PSHC3	0.700	
	PSHC4	0.727	
	PSHC5	0.711	
	PSHC6	0.738	
	PSHC7	0.763	
Consumer Lifestyle	CLS1	0.732	0.567
	CLS2	0.759	
	CLS3	0.780	
	CLS4	0.747	
	CLS5	0.745	
Social Media Influencer	SMI1	0.834	0.737
	SMI2	0.870	
	SMI3	0.882	
	SMI4	0.846	
Brand	BR1	0.684	0.579
	BR2	0.829	
	BR3	0.672	
	BR4	0.765	
	BR5	0.840	
Purchase Intention	PI1	0.761	0.582
	PI2	0.814	
	PI3	0.808	
	PI4	0.747	
	PI5	0.758	
	PI6	0.784	
	PI7	0.770	
	PI8	0.692	
	PI9	0.723	

Source: Based on this research

The AVE value on Perception of Second-hand Clothing (X1) is 0.514, Consumer Lifestyle (X2) is 0.567, Social Media Influencer (X3) is 0.737, Brand (X4) is 0.579, and Purchase Intention (Y) is 0.582. By looking at the data, it can be said that the value of all variables exceeds 0.5, which is the limit of the acceptance of the AVE value (Fornell and Larcker, 1981; Hair et al., 2017).

Then in Table 2, it can be seen that the loading item value for each indicator is more than 0.6, where the loading factor on the indicator variable Perception of Second-hand Clothing has a range of 0.670 – 0.763. Then, on the Consumer Lifestyle variable, each indicator also has a

loading factor value with a range of 0.732 – 0.780. The loading factor value on the Social Media Influencer indicator also has a vulnerability of 0.834 – 0.882. Next, followed by the Brand variable, which also has a vulnerable factor loading value of 0.684 – 0.840. Furthermore, finally, the factor loading value on the indicator of the Purchase Intention variable has a vulnerable value of 0.692 – 0.814. By looking at the data details above, it can be concluded that each indicator of each variable is valid and meets the criteria.

5.2.2 Discriminant Validity Analysis Discriminant

Validity testing aims to determine how much a construct differs from other constructs with empirical standards. In Table 3, it can be seen that the Fornell-Larcker Criterion value between the same variables is greater than the value between variables with other variables, showing that all questionnaire indicators are said to be valid.

Table 3: Validity - Fornell-Larcker Criterion

Construct	BR	CLS	PI	PSHC	SMI
BR	0.761				
CLS	0.753	0.613			
PI	PSHC	0.683	0.741		
0.763	0.541	0.702	0.717	0.716	
SMI	0.488	0.608	0.608	0.492	0.858

Source: Based on this research

Discriminant construct that is higher than the other constructs. Thus, it can be said that each construct that is formed is a unique construct and is different from other variables. It is said so because the correlation between latent variables with each indicator is more significant than the correlation with other latent variables.

Table 4: Discriminant Validity - Cross Loading Value

	BR	CLS	PI	PSHC	SMI
BR1	0,684	0,418	0,506	0,445	0,340
BR2	0,829	0,550	0,626	0,493	0,429
BR3	0,672	0,333	0,382	0,243	0,317
BR4	0,765	0,499	0,457	0,410	0,334
BR5	0,840	0,500	0,577	0,423	0,416
CLS1	0,376	0,732	0,577	0,558	0,460
CLS2	0,397	0,759	0,545	0,529	0,364
CLS3	0,487	0,780	0,542	0,574	0,393
CLS4	0,571	0,747	0,587	0,532	0,538
CLS5	0,473	0,745	0,531	0,497	0,527
PI1	0,539	0,567	0,761	0,529	0,383

PI2	0,548	0,622	0,814	0,581	0,417
PI3	0,555	0,607	0,808	0,608	0,465
PI4	0,491	0,548	0,747	0,541	0,438
PI5	0,542	0,594	0,758	0,558	0,528
PI6	0,516	0,610	0,784	0,558	0,525
PI7	0,482	0,568	0,770	0,530	0,485
PI8	0,510	0,470	0,692	0,438	0,450
PI9	0,503	0,480	0,723	0,459	0,499
PSHC1	0,331	0,450	0,465	0,670	0,337
PSHC2	0,326	0,430	0,437	0,706	0,335
PSHC3	0,396	0,547	0,532	0,700	0,264
PSHC4	0,414	0,581	0,578	0,727	0,403
PSHC5	0,383	0,514	0,470	0,711	0,405
PSHC6	0,425	0,507	0,467	0,738	0,369
PSHC7	0,426	0,536	0,546	0,763	0,358
SMI1	0,455	0,545	0,576	0,451	0,834
SMI2	0,446	0,505	0,490	0,412	0,870
SMI3	0,432	0,559	0,527	0,431	0,882
SMI4	0,334	0,469	0,491	0,389	0,846

Source: Based on this research

5.2.2 Construct Reliability Analysis

Methods in this study used Composite Reliability and Cronbach Alpha. As Fornell and Larcker (1981) recommended, the limit of Composite Reliability and Cronbach Alpha values that can be accepted in a test is 0.7. Table 5 shows that each Composite Reliability variable's value is 0.867 to 0.926. Then the same is the case with each variable's Cronbach Alpha value, which is in the number 0.809 – 0.91. Each number shown from each variable exceeds 0.7, which is the limit of the Composite Reliability and Cronbach Alpha values. Based on the data obtained, it is concluded that each variable has a high-reliability value, and each construct is said to be reliable. Thus, the measurement model presented quite fits the data for this study.

Table 5: Construct Reliability

Construct	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability
PSHC (X1)	0.843	0.881
CLS (X2)	0.809	0.867
SMI (X3)	0.881	0.918
BR (X4)	0.817	0.872
PI (Y)	0.910	0.926

Source: Based on this research

5.3 Evaluation of Structural Model

Refers to Chin (1998) criteria of R2 consists of three classifications: R2 0.67, 0.33, and 0.19 indicating a strong, moderate, and weak model. The structural analysis found that the r-square value on Perception of Second-hand Clothing, Customer Lifestyle, Social Media Influencer, Brand, and Purchasing Intention has a value of 0.69. These results can be interpreted that about 69% of a person's purchase intention to buy second-hand clothing is caused by the four latent constructions in the model.

Then, hypothesis testing was carried out on all samples obtained from the questionnaire. Table 6 shows that the value of the t-statistic on all variables is greater than 1.96, with a significant level of 95%. Then it was also found that the variables Perception of Second-hand Clothing (X1), Customer Lifestyle (X2), Social Media Influencer (X3), and Brand (X4) had a positive effect on Purchase Intention (Y).

Table 6: The result of structural model

Hypothesis		Sig. Level	Original Sample	T-Statistic	P Values	Hypothesis Support
H1	Perception of SHC (X1) → Purchase Intention (Y)	1.96	0.272	5.818	0.000	Positive, Significant Impact
H2	Consumer Lifestyle (X2) → Purchase Intention (Y)	1.96	0.261	4.600	0.000	Positive, Significant Impact
H3	Social Media Influencer (X3) → Purchase Intention (Y)	1.96	0.176	3.994	0.000	Positive, Significant Impact
H4	Brand (X4) → Purchase Intention (Y)	1.96	0.289	6.457	0.000	Positive, Significant Impact

Source: Based on this research

6.0 DISCUSSION

The popularity of thrifting activity among Generation Z in Indonesia makes this research interested in predicting the relationship between Perception of Second-hand Clothing (SHC), Consumer Lifestyle, Social Media Influencers, and Brands on Purchase Intention of second-hand clothing (thrifting). From the research data obtained, hypothesis testing has been carried out where the test results can be concluded that all of the proposed hypotheses are accepted, which means that the four variable constructs positively influence purchase intention.

The results showed that Perception of Second-hand Clothing (SHC) positively related to Purchase Intention in 'thrifting'. That is, how one view SHC will be able to influence purchase intention in 'thrifting' or buying second-hand clothing. These results can be seen in Table 6, which shows that the t-statistic value has a value of 5.818. The construct of Perception of SHC

itself consists of 3 indicators, that is socio-environmental awareness, preconception with second-hand clothes, and need for personal uniqueness. This finding follows research conducted by Amaral and Spers (2022) which states that indicators of socio-environmental awareness and the need for personal uniqueness in the Perception of SHC positively affect the purchase intention of second-hand clothing.

It can happen because most people are aware of the environment and assume that buying second-hand clothing can help protect the environment. They also stated that thrifting activity or buying second-hand clothing has its charm or uniqueness because the clothes sold by the thrift shop are not sold in large quantities in one model or can be said to be a limited-edition product.

However, compared to the preconception indicator with second-hand clothes, which does not influence the Perception of SHC that can affect purchase intention. This study found that the preconception of second-hand clothes indicator on the Perception of SHC variable positively influenced purchase intention on second-hand clothing (thrifting). Because most people think that the hygiene of second-hand clothes is essential to pay attention to, they stated that they considered that second-hand clothing was still guaranteed clean and hygienic after they rewashed it. They also consider that second-hand clothing is still appropriate for them to wear.

In H2, it is found that Consumer Lifestyle affects Purchase Intention on 'thrifting'. This can be seen in Table 6, which shows that Consumer Lifestyle has a t-statistic value of 4,600. This finding supports the hypothesis that there is a significant relationship between Consumer Lifestyle. In addition, this finding also supports the statement of Hawkins et al. (2010), which states that a person's way of life will be able to affect all aspects of a person's consumption. Where one of the aspects of a person's consumption is the consumer purchase intention, this can happen because most consumers think that second-hand clothing is still comfortable to wear for everyday use. Not only have that, in their daily life they choose to wear clothes that tend to be liked in terms of model and quality.

It is well known that 'thrifting' is one of the fashion trends in the midst of generation Z. In this study, most of the people agreed that they did thrifting to follow the fashion trend, which became a lifestyle for a person. This finding also supports previous Sakti et al. (2020) research, which states that consumer lifestyle significantly influences buying interest, especially in fashion. These findings also align with Rudianto (2021) research, which states that a person's lifestyle affects purchase intention in purchasing clothes.

Furthermore, the results of this study indicate that H3 is accepted, that is Social Media Influencers have a positive relationship with Purchase Intention on second-hand clothing (thrifting). This statement can be seen from the t-statistic value in Table 6, which reached 3,994. This finding is in accordance with the statement of Chekima et al. (2020), which states that social media influencers have a positive relationship with purchase intention. In addition, keep in mind that three indicators of influencers must be considered, namely attractiveness, trustworthiness, and expertise. Because these indicators are considered to have a significant

influence on influencers, and in the end, these influencers can influence purchasing decisions by consumers (Alfarraj, 2021).

In this study, it can be said that the content delivered by social media influencers regarding thrifting can make people interested in doing it. However, this interest cannot be separated from the trustworthiness of the community towards the influencer, and most of the public stated that the influencer's content and messages about 'thrifting' conveyed can be trusted because they assume that the influencer who conveys it, has sufficient knowledge (expertise) about a product being delivered. With the results obtained, it is not surprising that influencers are often used as third parties who help in marketing a business to determine someone's attitude (Freberg et al., 2011). The test results on H4 show that the brand has a positive relationship with Purchase Intention on 'thrifting'. The statement is based on Table 6 shows the t-statistic value on the brand of 6,457. Where this number is the most significant number of other t-statistic values. So, it can be said that brand has the most significant influence on Purchase Intention. In the Brand variable, there are two indicators in it, namely brand image and brand awareness. So that indirectly, brand image and brand awareness. This study found that most consumers consider the brand of second-hand clothing important to pay attention to. In addition, second-hand from well-known brands or brands that consumers know tend to be chosen because they believe in the brand's quality.

This statement is in line with the thoughts of Godey et al. (2016), which state that brand image and awareness contribute to customer loyalty, brand preference, and purchase intention, which ultimately becomes a purchase decision. In addition, a brand is also believed to influence consumers' pride, confidence, and enthusiasm (Kotler and Keller, 2016). This statement is also in line with the results of research, where most consumers state that the brand is essential for them when doing thrifting.

7.0 CONCLUSION

This study examines the relationship between Perception of Second-hand Clothing, Consumer Lifestyle, Social Media Influencers, and Brand on Purchase Intention on 'thrifting'. The research was conducted by surveying 390 Generation Z in Jakarta, Bogor, Depok, Tangerang, and Bekasi, located in Indonesia. Data processing is carried out using the SEM-PLS application. The results of this study indicate that Perception of Second-hand Clothing, Consumer Lifestyle, Social Media Influencers, and Brands have a positive relationship with Purchase Intention on Thrifting. Based on the study's results, it was also found that the 'thrifting' activity was mainly carried out by women and those aged 20 – 22 years with an expenditure level of <Rp 1,200,000. Uniquely, some of them, whose level of expenditure is in the middle to the upper category, are still doing thrifting. Thus, indirectly thrifting activities are not only carried out by lower or middle-class people. However, thrifting is carried out by all economic circles, even though the number from the middle to the upper category is only a tiny part.

This study found that Perception of Second-hand Clothing, Consumer Lifestyle, Social Media Influencers, and Brands had a positive relationship. It was also found that in second-hand clothing, a brand is essential for Z-generation to pay attention to. Apart from being a well-

known brand, they believe that 'branded' second-hand clothing still has good quality. Then, most people said they did thrifting because they wanted to follow the fashion trend. This finding indirectly proves that thrifting is a fashion that is currently becoming a trend in Indonesia, especially in generation Z. In addition, people think that wearing second-hand clothing gives them their own uniqueness because most of the clothes sold by thrift shops are limited edition products.

Based on the study's results, recommendations can be drawn for similar industries to pay attention to several factors that can influence people's buying intentions on second-hand clothing. It is also essential to pay attention to how to promote the products being sold, namely by using social media influencers' services. However, you still have to pay attention to attractive influencers, good knowledge of 'thrifting', and influencers trusted by the community. In addition, to increase the possibility of sales, pay attention to the types of products sold because most people stated that the model, quality, and brand of second-hand clothing are essential to pay intention to. In addition, this study found that most people are willing and willing to find out more about 'thrifting', then recommend it to others, be it friends, relatives, or family. Then, the framework in this research can also be used as a reference for academics interested in studying the concept of purchase intention in Generation Z, especially in the fashion sector. Furthermore, this research contributes to the addition of existing insights and literature regarding the Perception of Second-hand Clothing, Consumer Lifestyle, Social Media Influencers, brands, and their relationship with Purchase Intention on second-hand clothing. This study also has limitations, such as the research only focusing on Generation Z, who live in several regions of Indonesia, namely Jakarta, Bogor, Depok, Tangerang, and Bekasi (Jabodetabek). In addition, to those who have done 'thrifting' in the past year.

This study examines the perception of second-hand clothing and consumer lifestyle. Where each region certainly has a different perception and lifestyle. Also, social media influencers and brands in second-hand clothing products do not necessarily have the same influence in other areas. Therefore, further researchers need to include samples from various ages or generations and other regions from around the world to find cross-cultural evaluations, effects, and variations in aspects of purchase intention in society. Thus, it is possible to compare purchase intention motives in the community, especially in the fashion industry. Future research is also expected to focus on 'thrifting', so that more insights and knowledge can be provided.

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